

**FIRST RECORD OF *OESTOPHORA BARBULA* (ROSSMÄSSLER 1838)
(PULMONATA, HELICIDAE) ON MADEIRA.¹**

by

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While investigating the terrestrial mollusca-fauna of the Madeiran archipelago we collected at the western and south-western slopes of the Central-Madeiran mountain Pico do Serrado, facing the village Curral das Freiras, on the 27. VII 1985. Between 1000 m and the top of the Pico (1099 m) we found — mainly under big stones but also beneath rotted logs — numerous specimens of a gastropod obviously belonging to the subfamily of Helicodontinae. This species was not known to us from the Madeiran fauna.

Comparison with specimens of *Oestophora barbula* (Rossmässler, 1838) in the collections of the authors and the Senckenberg-Museum Frankfurt/M. proved that we had found this species now in the Madeira island, from where it not had been reported before (cfr. e.g. NOBRE, 1931, WALDÉN, 1983). *O. barbula* is widely distributed in Portugal (NOBRE, 1941) and Northern Spain, mainly in cultivated areas. Additionally this species also occupies all islands of the Azores archipelago, except the island os Santa Maria (BACKHUYS 1975).

Although BACKHUYS states, that *O. barbula* may be autochthonous on the Azores islands, we have some doubts. It may have been introduced by human being after the Portuguese started the colonisation in the 15th century. Especially the gap of distribution on the islands of Santa Maria and the whole Madeiran archipelago gives evidence that we have to calculate *O. barbula* as a neozoon on all Atlantic islands — even it may have reached the Azores before it's first reported occurrence on Faial island by FORBES (1852).

As this is the first record of the species from Madeira, we are quite sure that *O. barbula* has been introduced by man in very recent times. This introduction may have happened in the same area after 1980, as the first author and his wife CHRISTINA collected here for some hours on 2.. XI. 1980 and could not find a single animal of the species.

It is striking, that most of the collected specimens (Fig. 7 A, B) have a rather strong dentition of the aperture. Normally this is rare in the populations of the

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1) Beiträge zur Kenntnis der Mollusken des Madeira Archipels, Nr. 10. — Nr. 9: On the nomenclatoric status of *Helix wollastoni* LOWE and *H. forensis* WOLLASTON. — Bocagiana; Funchal (in press).

Portuguese mainland. Furthermore the size of the specimens from Madeira is significant lower than those of Portuguese animals (width of shell 10 to 11.5 mm instead of 13 to 15 mm; cfr. NOBRE 1941). Both facts are additional hints to believe that the initial population of the Pico do Serrado was quite small. The fact that the species became predominant within only few years is nevertheless a proof for the high fitness of the ancestors.

The habitat where *O. barbula* has been found on Madeira is a light, perhaps 60 to 80 years old forest of *Pinus pinaster* AIT. (Fig. 1). There is nearly no herbaceous vegetation, but there exist many mosses and lichenes on the rocks. As the slopes of the Pico do Serrado are very steep there is a very intensive terracing. The only significant autochthonous elements of the flora are some shrubs of *Erica* sp.

Also the accompanying fauna of terrestrial mollusca is highly influenced by anthropochorous species, which are signaled by and asterix (*) in the following list:

Ferussaciidae *Amphorella* (A.) *tornatellina* (Lowe 1831) / **Arionidae** *Arion* (A.) *lusitanicus* Mabille 1968*
Limacidae *Limax* (L.) *maximus* Linnaeus 1758* / **Agriolimacidae** *Deroceras* sp.* / **Helicidae** *Caseolus* (C.)
c. compactus (Lowe 1831)

It is worth to note that the population of *O. barbula* on the Pico do Serrado seems to be quite big, as it is reported by NOBRE (1941) for those of the Portuguese mainland. As this species is highly expansive and has a wide ecological valence, we have no doubt, that it will be established also in other areas of the island in the near future. So it may be a danger for the many autochthonous and endemic species of shells, which have a lower ecological range and live partly only in very restricted areas of Madeira. Nevertheless a control of *O. barbula* would be only possible by chemical molluscicides, whose effectivity seems not high enough to destroy the — even small — population, but would effect much more negative influence on the autochthonous molluscs.

RESUMO

Os autores dão notícia da ocorrência, na ilha da Madeira, da *Oestophora barbula* Ross., até agora não indicada para a região.

Perante a distribuição geográfica conhecida para a espécie, admitem tratar-se de uma introdução recente, provavelmente de agente humano.

LITERATURE CITED

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- (1941) — Fauna malacológica de Portugal II. — Moluscos terrestres e fluviais. — Mém. Est. Mus. Zool. Univ. Coimbra, 124, 277 + 1 + 2 pp., 30 pls.; Coimbra.
- WALDÉN, H. W. (1983) — Systematic and biogeographical studies on the terrestrial gastropoda of Madeira. — With an annotated check-list. — Ann. Zool. Fennici, 20: 255-275; Helsingfors.

7

A

B

C

FIGURA 7

- A — B — *Oestophora barbula* (Rossmässler 1838), Madeira, Pico do Serrado, 27. VII. 1985, leg. J. HEMMEN & K. GROH. — Figured specimen deposited in Museu Municipal do Funchal. (Foto José Silva).
- C — Habitat of *Oestophora barbula* on Madeira: The top of the Pico do Serrado with a forest of *Pinus pinaster*, seen from Curral das Freiras, north of the mountain.